

ISic1118

I.Sicily inscription 1118

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

tuff

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Θεόδοτα Κέλτα

2. Ἐπαφρόδειτε

3. χάρε

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492732

EDR 140731

EDCS 39102274

PHI 140602

PHI 175743

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0298 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika* 6. Palermo. At 138

Bechtel, F., Collitz, H., Meister, R. C., Bezenberger, A. 1884-1915. Sammlung der griechischen Dialekt-Inschriften. Göttingen. At 5195

Ferrua, A 1941. Epigrafica sicula pagana e cristiana. *Rivista di archeologia cristiana*. 18: 151-243. At 231 no.1

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1118. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4351545>